

Exploring unpleasant feelings elicited from assistive products in two studies with young adults

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Abstract

Assistive products may elicit unpleasant feelings within both the actual user and persons around. By analysing two complementary studies, this paper tries to illuminate which unpleasant feelings may be elicited. In study A industrial design students evaluated assistive products. In study B young persons with disabilities were interviewed about their everyday experiences. Negative statements by participants in both studies were divided into three categories: Identity, Experiences through senses, and Functionality. Expressed feelings of disgust, dislike, irritation, frustration, disappointment, boredom and unattractiveness were identified. When a mismatch in identity between user and product existed, actual users as well as students referred to unpleasant feelings. Students were more sensitive regarding unpleasant feelings elicited from senses than from functionality. They acted as consumers before a possible purchase. Persons with disabilities focused on feelings elicited from functionality since they already possessed and were used to their products. It is important for a designer of assistive products to have an open mind regarding which unpleasant feelings may be elicited within the context of the user with disability, the assistive product and people around the user.

Key words: Emotions, unpleasant feelings, assistive products, industrial design, salutogenic

Introduction

Carefully designed everyday products for users with disabilities will increase their independence, activity, well-being and self esteem. How will products that may elicit an unpleasant feeling affect the self-concept, i.e. ideas, feelings and attitudes an individual see within her or himself? How does the user interact with such an artefact? Products that are initially designed to meet both functional and emotional needs will be experienced positively by the users, contribute to their pride and even a strengthened self-concept. A product designed to be usable to the greatest extent possible by all ages and abilities (Story et al, 1998) can be defined as a universal design product. Pleasurable products with a universal design perspective will probably also have a positive influence on how others look upon and approach the user.

Today, assistive products have a low market share compared to ordinary everyday products, as most manufacturing companies do not operate towards persons with disability as customers. They are rarely even seen as customers of assistive products; other actors order and prescribe the assistive product for a consumer who later will become the user. A person who needs a specific assistive product will have to be satisfied regardless of how he or she experiences its aesthetic qualities and simply has to take what is offered in order to manage the day.

Using a salutogenic approach to design means to identify and strengthen those aspects of artefacts which help us to cope with adversities. The concept salutogenic (Antonovsky, 1987) builds upon sense of coherence, to optimise one's chance to handle a situation or a problem and can be divided into three different categories: (1) Comprehensible; understand the problem, (2) Manageable; have sufficient resources at ones disposal and (3) Meaningful; wish to cope with the problem, which is the most important category. Ilstedt-Hjelm (2004) translated Antonovsky's concept into products. How to successfully interact with an object? Here "Meaningful" stands for the user's motivation to connect with the object – that the object is of emotional significance. If the user feels meaninglessness when interacting with a product, it might spread the feeling to other parts of life and in the long run hurt the user emotionally, which can result in burnout or depression. A product which the user does not wish to interact with will not be considered as meaningful for that person, and such a product will elicit emotions, which will be expressed in unpleasant feelings.

Emotions are a complex interaction between body and mind. There are different aspects of a product that may elicit emotions in users, such as aesthetics, functionality, brand and personal associations. Emotions are personal and individual experiences, and different persons express different emotions towards the same situation, event or physical objects. The elicited emotion should not be seen as a feature of the design, but a subjective experience of the user, owner or person looking at someone using the product. Desmet (2002) described and classified 14 product-relevant emotions into five emotional types; instrumental, aesthetic, social, surprise and interest. Even if emotions are idiosyncratic, the conditions that underlie and elicit them are universal. These underlying emotional responses form patterns. Further Desmet (2002) means, that a designer can use these patterns for developing their personal sensitivity for recognising the eliciting conditions of product emotions.

Product values are related with each other. Ottosson (2004) described user product values as divided into three different categories: functional, sensual (perceptual) and image values. Functional values have to do with good function of products and are in general hidden within the product. Sensual values come to us from/through the surfaces of the product. Image values represent the appearance the product has in our minds as a virtual product. These product values represent characteristics that should present the product to the user in the stage where a potential buyer becomes an owner. Consumers acknowledge soft values - sensual and image values- to a higher degree than only considering the fulfilment of functional values (Ottosson, 2004) when they stands in front of the decision buying or not buying a product. This is in agreement with Hasdogan (1996) who stated that consumers only considerate for example cost, appearance and brand image and do not include usability or functionality since they are only potential and not necessarily actual users.

Sensual values could be divided into how different senses are used to interpret products, i.e. if the user interprets through visual or tactile experiences. The dominant sense is the visual, what we often see frequently reflect our feeling about products. Visual combined with the tactile sense often makes our argument if we like the product or not (Monö, 1997).

Eikelenberg et al (2002) conclude that comfort and satisfaction cannot be discussed in isolation; they should always be seen in an integrative approach. These arguments translated to feelings might be expressed as; pleasant feelings are associated with both emotional and physical aspects of products and unpleasant feelings with absence of physical aspects. An

unpleasant emotion elicited from senses never stand alone, it is always integrated with a product's functionality.

The aim of the present paper is to illuminate unpleasant feelings elicited by assistive products in their relationship to disabled users as well as others, by analysing data from two studies with novice and expert users. The data is systematised in order to investigate what kinds of unpleasant feelings are described by the participants and how descriptions differ between both groups. An expert user (Hasdogan, 1996) has developed his own practice for using a product whether or not it matches the recommended usage.

Methods

Two studies were taken further into an analysis of expressed unpleasant feelings towards products for users with disabilities. Study A (Olander et al, 2005) was an attempt to make universal design an integral part of industrial design by means of an experiment which was implemented early in the industrial design education. Study B (Olander, 2006), is an empirical study based on semi-structured interviews with young adults with various disabilities regarding products in their surroundings. Both studies explore expressed feelings regarding products but with two different approaches.

In study A, 25 first year industrial design students took part. The aim was to increase the awareness of students regarding the fact that products may at the same time be attractive and well-functioning for a wide range of users. The students were divided into five groups. All groups evaluated five categories of everyday products (pencils, knives, cheese slicers, cups and telephones). Each category contained five objects covering a range from stylish or sporty to assistive products. The student groups tried the objects at use and rated and commented on three mainly emotional and three mainly functional product values represented by adjectives in a questionnaire. A visual analogue scale was used for rating of qualities.

For the present study the young adults were regarded novice users, since they had no previous experience of using the assistive products included in the study. They may also be regarded as observers of the disabled users since they are building their comments in a context where somebody else is the "real" user. The analysis of unpleasant feelings included 12 products from the originally 25. Of the 12 products nine were assistive products and three were universal design products. Universal design in this case means that the products were

originality designed as assistive products but are now marketed in shops for everyday commodities and bought by anyone.

In study B, 10 young adults with disabilities related to vision, hearing and mobility, were interviewed regarding their experiences about any products in their surroundings. The aim was to investigate emotional aspects, i.e. sensual and image values, of products in everyday life in order to identify emotional relationships between users and products. Interview questions were semi-structured, focusing on four thematic questions. The questions had a broad approach and included experiences related to products, activities and situations. It was tried to reach products from four different perspectives: importance, positive or negative experiences and identity. It was up to the interview person to choose experiences to mediate, and consequently topics to be discussed differed from person to person. The mediated experiences from the interviews were analysed with an attitude inspired from Grounded Theory (Glaser et al, 1967), i.e. the analysis took place parallel with the data collection. The parallel analysis affected the interview questions; they changed during time, and the selection of interview persons.

For the present analysis of unpleasant feelings, six out of ten interviews were taken into consideration, covering persons with experience living with sight, hearing and physical disabilities. Only statements regarding explicitly assistive products were analysed. The young adults are regarded expert users, since they have a current everyday perspective of assistive products.

The chosen data from both studies was analysed by a similar process although their character and intensity were different. Data from each study (A and B) were first separately organised into three categories i.e. positive, negative or neutral statements. A neutral statement means that no explicit judgements are given. Next phase in the analysis, data still separated, was to focus on the negative statements alone. The negative experiences/statements were forming a pattern which could be connected to image, sensual and function product values (Ottosson, 2004). This contributed to sort the data into five subcategories: image/identity, visual experiences, tactile experiences, functionality and others. When both studies were sorted into these five subcategories, the process to find similarities and differences between the two groups started.

Results

Novices as well as experts expressed several negative statements about assistive products regarding identity, experiences through senses and functionality.

Identity. If products send wrong messages about whom the user is or is expected to be, both novices and experts react with unpleasant feelings. For example even if a product is supposed to be used by a person of the same age and in the same context as the novices, the latter reflect that the assistive product looks as if it is a product for a small child or to be used by someone staying at a hospital (comments about a cup with cover and spout for persons with difficulties to hold things in their hands). Another product, a knife with an angled handle (e.g. for persons with rheumatoid arthritis), is regarded a saw for carpentry, instead of a kitchen tool, sending a wrong message or expectation about what the product is intended for. The novices comment that a product is not for them, which regards all nine assistive products: it is made for somebody else, a child, a disabled person or an elderly at an institution. They use words as childish, ridiculous, absurd, disfigured, senior citizen, to describe the product and at the same time they refer to the fact that they are not target users. This clearly demonstrates that novices cannot identify themselves with the product and they express unpleasant feelings as disgust.

The experts' comments confirm that assistive products send out wrong messages. Two persons feel as if people lack respect for their assistive product (wheel chairs), which they have to rely on to manage their daily lives. Sometimes a person takes a step too close, ending up inside the user's personal territory, eliciting an unpleasant feeling. The compensatory product is seen as any product, and not a product with a strong connection to its user. An assistive product may not match the user's self-concept (i.e. a white stick or hearing aids). This occurs when the product does not correspond to the user as a personal being or how the user wants others to look up on him or her. Some of the experts refer that they totally avoid using a specific assistive product or sometimes actively choose in which context they use them (not using a white stick in front of a cash dispenser because of the increased risk of getting robbed). Using the avoided product would have facilitated their day, but they just cannot identify themselves with the product's message.

Experiences through senses. Both visual and tactile experiences show that some of the assistive products are not appealing to neither novices nor experts. The strongest unpleasant feelings are found among the novices, but even some of the experts express that they dislike

some of the assistive products because of how they look or feel. Novices regard almost all assistive products as ugly, with boring and strange colours; some of the assistive products are made of white plastic material (a cup and knife), a colour which they associated with clinical contexts. The novices also give remarks about the products surface material; that it looks or feels cheap elicited as dissatisfaction and disappointment, as if neither designer nor producer has made an effort to make the product holistic and pleasant. Two of the cups look as if they are composed by different parts not fitting together, neither in form nor in material, lacking a feeling of quality and user dignity. Novices clearly express unattractiveness and could not see themselves as buyers. In some cases the novices experience a product as something distasteful or unappetizing (knives, cups) even though the products were fresh from the store and had not been used before. Choice of material was one reason for experiencing the product as un-fresh, not handsome or crummy (telephones). The tactile experiences strengthen the unpleasant visual feelings; also touch of materials seems to contribute to reactions. Novices express that a synthetic rubber material feels adhesive in their hands (cheese slicers). Shape is reported as clumsy or knobby; it is not comfortable to hold (cups). Other tactile experiences give impressions of insecurity, that the product can hurt you, such as sharp edges and parting lines of cups may hurt your hand.

The experts are less expressive regarding sensual experiences. One person comments on a kitchen with height adjustable cabinets which she refused to have in her home. This person express dislikes how the kitchen looks like (ugly), its size (too big) and its sound (too much noise). Another example is an assistive standing support eliciting disgust; looking like a hybrid between a thing from an institute for long-time care during the 70s and Frankenstein's laboratory.

Functionality. Results related to this category are different from the previously mentioned. The experts give more expressions than the novices. They express that emotions such as irritation or frustrations are elicited from products not functioning as they are supposed to. One example describes a cash dispenser with speech function, where there is a button among all others on the product, marked with Braille for explaining the speech function, giving a promise to the disabled person that the company made an effort, but no speech function is in fact installed in the product. He or she must instead look for another cash dispenser somewhere else. Regarding the kitchen with adjustable cabinets; the expert expresses frustration when lacking control, i.e. if somebody else would adjust the kitchen. The kitchen

also elicits irritation about the time it takes to readjust, even if it is just about seconds. If many activities take extra seconds they may all together elicit stress. A third example is the fact that experts have to carry around a lot of extra products to enable use of their everyday products, i.e. for mobile phones and computers, instead of providing products with integrated functions. A last example is a soft-ware for computers that helps blowing up information on the screen for persons with impaired vision. The program shows just a small fragment at a time from the internet site, resulting in the fact that the user misses the whole picture. This is time consuming as information is often missed because of lost orientation on the screen.

In general novices are satisfied with the function of the assistive products. They are disappointed about how the product is seized, the product mismatches hand size or angled handles of knife and cheese-slicers take to much storing place in the kitchen. Cups and telephones also elicit irritation when tried, such as hard to clean (cups are difficult to take apart) and clumsy.

Discussion

The two analysed studies with students and users with disabilities respectively were not designed to be comparative and consequently it is not possible to make exact comparisons. They should instead be seen as complementary and contributing to a wider picture for designers, feeding them with an open attitude. Results of the present study illuminate which unpleasant feelings to have in mind when creating assistive products. Feelings are individual and dependent of product and context of use and are not possible to treat as something absolute or regular in all situations. We have tried to make both groups of data complementary to each other by practising similar tactics in analysis of both studies - fitting data through the same strainer - and having an open attitude towards findings.

Persons in both studies express unpleasant feelings regarding Identity, which is one of the categories of the analysis. The assistive products seem to send out something perceived as wrong messages regarding identity and image, the product and person respectively, to both the real user (expert) and persons just looking at a product. When a product is tried, one feels something, as a bodily response, elicited from a mind activity (Cupchik, 2002). The knife with an angled handle was identified as another tool, a saw. The bodily response is a feeling of uncertainty or disbelief, since you were told it is a knife – mind is controlling body (Cupchik, 2002). The students (novices) refer to already existing target groups, children or

disabled persons, already by the product's visual form. Such a product is definitively not an object they are attracted to or would buy for themselves. They describe products in words as ugly or ridiculous and, at the same time, ascribe them to other persons than themselves, disabled persons, not individuals with disabilities. Consequently, a young person with a disability, only by using such as product, sends a message to his/her onlookers: I am different from you. The ultimate consequence is that persons with disabilities, as some of the interviewed persons, do not use such products, even if they know that they could be helped by them; the products do not match their self-concepts. A person with a visual impairment has the full understanding that life would be easier if she used a white stick and she manages to handle it, but yet cannot see her self using it, because of the product's image. It does not fit with her self-concept, how she wants others to look on her, resulting in the fact that she feels neither the need nor the wish to use it - the product has no meaning to her. Even if two of Antonovsky's (1987) categories (Comprehensible and Manageable) are fulfilled, it is not enough if the third one (Meaningful) is not.

When it comes to the categories Experiences by senses and Functionality, the students give more comments expressing unpleasant feelings by senses (vision and touch) than persons with disabilities, who are more expressive as to functionality. Students report that they experience products as unattractive or with unpleasant materials and without a feeling of quality, which seems to elicit feelings such as disgust and boredom. Your visual and tactile impressions are in your mind compared with experiences of other similar products and then send out a feeling of dissatisfaction. However, students are surprised about the products' function: in general they mean that these are well-functioning already after having tried them just once. This is in contrast to the interview persons who use their assistive products daily and give several reports about absent or not fulfilled functional qualities resulting in elicited feelings as frustration, irritation or disappointment. For expert users absence or not fulfilled function seems to be dominant, while experiences by senses provide potential users with their first impressions, as is the case in the novice users of the present study. Comments by the interview persons expressed as unpleasant feelings by vision, such as about the kitchen cabinets and the standing support, these products are in fact not used by them – they have just participated in a demonstration by somebody else, like the students experiences from the evaluated products. A question to be raised is if unpleasant feelings are consistent over time. An assistive product such as a standing support might elicit unpleasant feelings immediately after interaction with the potential user (consumer), as to sensual and image but not functional

values. If a product makes its user feel healthier or feel less pain, this will after a time probably contribute to pleasant feelings and to improved well-being.

As a designer of products for persons with disabilities, it is important to have a salutogenic approach towards the products you create, especially to make the product elicit meaning to the user, in such a way that the user wants to interact with it. In summary, the results from the present analysis demonstrate that unpleasant feelings such as disgust, dislike, disrespectfulness, a feeling of being an outsider might be elicited from assistive products if a user does not experience the product as meaningful, in a way that he/she does not wish to connect with the object. Or when our social emotions, which are elicited from our standard, moral and judgemental evaluation, do not match the message/image the product sends out. Other unpleasant feelings such as disgust, boredom, dislike, irritation and insecurity might also be elicited from assistive products when the user's attitudes towards the products are mismatched. Such attitudes are formed by the user's aesthetic values towards product features as form, material and colour. Finally, unpleasant feelings as disappointment, irritation, dissatisfaction and frustration may be elicited when a user does not understand the object.

Conclusions

If a designer is aware of what might elicit unpleasant feelings he or she can integrate this knowledge in a salutogenic design of an assistive product. A person with a disability will experience a strengthened self-concept when meeting the product and will increase his/her willingness to use it; the product will feel meaningful and the person will be less depending on others. Hopefully this will also contribute to a changed attitude towards assistive products among people around persons with disabilities. Assistive products will be desirable to all persons instead of being something that separate users with disabilities from others.

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